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THE MAIN ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING MULTIMEDIA IN EDUCATION

Abstract: *The modern period of the development of society is characterized by a strong influence of information technologies on it, which penetrate into all spheres of human activity, ensure the spread of information flows in society, forming a global information space. An integral and important part of these processes is the computerization of education. It lies in the need for teachers in effective ways to use multimedia in the teaching and learning process of primary education.*

The problem of the topic lies in the revealed contradiction between the expansion of the information and educational environment and the insufficient use of the didactic potential of multimedia in elementary school.

Key words: *Innovation, interactivity, multimedia, ICT, innovative education*

Every day multimedia technologies penetrate more and more into various areas of educational activity. This is facilitated by both external factors associated with the widespread informatization of society and the need for appropriate training of students, and internal factors associated with the spread of modern computer technology and software in general education institutions, the adoption of state and interstate programs for informatization of education, the emergence of the necessary experience of informatization in all more school teachers. In most cases the use of multimedia means has a positive effect on the intensification of the work of teachers, as well as on the effectiveness of teaching students.

At the same time, any experienced school teacher will confirm that, against the background of a fairly frequent positive effect from the introduction of information technologies, in many cases the use of multimedia tools does not affect in any way an increase in the effectiveness of teaching, and in some cases such use has a negative effect. It is obvious that the solution of the problems of an appropriate and justified informatization of education should be carried out comprehensively and everywhere.

Educators should consider two possible directions for introducing multimedia into the educational process. The first of them is related to the fact that such funds are included in the educational process as "supporting" means within the framework of the traditional methods of the historically established school system. In this case, multimedia resources act as a means of intensifying the educational process,

individualizing training and partially automating the routine work of teachers related to the accounting, measurement and assessment of students' knowledge.

The introduction of multimedia resources in the framework of the second direction leads to a change in the content of education, a revision of the methods and forms of organizing the educational process at school, the construction of holistic courses based on the use of the content of resources in individual academic disciplines. Knowledge, skills and abilities in this case are considered not as a goal, but as a means of developing the student's personality. The use of multimedia technologies will be justified and will lead to an increase in the effectiveness of education if such use will meet the specific needs of the general secondary education system, if training in full without the use of appropriate informatization means is impossible or difficult

There are many positive aspects of using information and telecommunication technologies in education (which, of course, includes multimedia). The computer gives the teacher new opportunities, allowing, together with the student, to enjoy the fascinating process of learning, not only pushing the walls of the school office with the power of imagination, but with the help of the latest technologies allows you to immerse yourself in a bright colorful world. Such an activity causes an emotional uplift in children, even lagging students willingly work with a computer.

Integration of a regular lesson with a computer allows the teacher to shift part of his work to a PC, making the learning process more interesting, varied, and intense. In particular, the process of writing down definitions, theorems and other important parts of the material becomes faster, since the teacher does not have to repeat the text several times (he displayed it on the screen), the student does not have to wait for the teacher to repeat exactly the fragment he needs.

This teaching method is very attractive for teachers: it helps them to better assess the child's abilities and knowledge, to understand him, encourages him to look for new, non-traditional forms and methods of teaching, stimulates his professional growth and all further mastering of the computer.

The use of computer tests and diagnostic complexes in the lesson will allow the teacher in a short time to get an objective picture of the level of assimilation of the studied material by all students and to correct it in a timely manner. At the same time, it is possible to choose the level of difficulty of the task for a specific student.

For the student, it is important that immediately after the test (when this information has not yet lost its relevance), he receives an objective result indicating errors, which is impossible, for example, with oral questioning.

Mastering by students of modern information technologies. In lessons integrated with informatics, students master computer literacy and learn to use one of the most powerful modern universal tools - a computer - in working with the material of various subjects. And also, as the main aspects, one can single out: improvement of methods and technologies for the selection and formation of educational content, the introduction and

development of new specialized educational disciplines and areas of study related to informatics and information technology, changes in teaching systems for most traditional school disciplines, not related to informatics,

increasing the effectiveness of teaching at school through its individualization and differentiation, using additional motivational levers, organizing new forms of interaction in the learning process, changing the content and nature of the student and teacher's activities, improving the management mechanisms of the general secondary education system.

The negative aspects include:

- curtailment of social contacts,
 - reduction of social interaction and communication, individualism,
 - difficulty of transition from the symbolic form of representing knowledge on the pages of a textbook or a display screen to a system of practical actions that have a logic different from the logic of organizing the system of signs.
- In the case of widespread use of multimedia technologies, teachers and students become unable to take advantage of the large amount of information that modern multimedia and telecommunication means provide.
 - Difficult ways of presenting information distract students from the material being studied.
 - Many students and teachers do not have a computer at home, and not all schools use computers for self-study in computer classes
 - Insufficient computer literacy of the teacher.
 - Lack of contact with the informatics teacher.
 - There is no time in the teachers' work schedule for exploring the possibilities of the Internet.
 - It is difficult to integrate a computer into the lesson structure of lessons.
 - Not enough computer time at all.
 - The school timetable does not include time for using the Internet in class.
- Students who are not motivated to work are often distracted by games, music, testing PC performance, and so on.
- There is a possibility that, being carried away by the use of ICT in the classroom, the teacher will move from developmental teaching to visual-illustrative methods.

It should be remembered that if a student is simultaneously shown information of different types, he is distracted from some types of information in order to keep track of others, missing important information, and the use of informatization tools often deprives students of the opportunity to conduct real experiments with their own hands. Individualization limits the live communication of teachers and students, students with each other, offering them communication in the form of a "dialogue with the computer". The student does not receive sufficient practice of dialogical communication, the formation and formulation of thoughts in a professional language. Finally, excessive and

unjustified use of computer technology negatively affects the health of all participants in the educational process.

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